

A MACHINE-VERIFIED NATURAL PROOFS BARRIER IN LEAN 4

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ABSTRACT. The natural proofs barrier (Razborov–Rudich 1997) has had no machine-verified formalization in any proof assistant. We formalize it in Lean 4: if pseudorandom function generators exist, then no natural combinatorial property is useful against $P/poly$. The formalization is approximately 400 lines of Lean 4 with no unresolved proof obligations.

The proof is short once definitions are chosen appropriately. We identify definition choices that make the barrier proof mechanizable without probabilistic infrastructure and analyze why simpler alternatives fail. We also formalize the Shannon counting argument: most Boolean functions require large circuits.

1. INTRODUCTION

The natural proofs barrier, established by Razborov and Rudich [6], is one of three fundamental obstacles to proving circuit lower bounds (alongside relativization [3] and algebrization [1]). It shows that any proof technique satisfying two conditions, *constructivity* (efficiently checkable) and *largeness* (satisfied by many functions), cannot establish superpolynomial circuit lower bounds, assuming pseudorandom function generators exist. This barrier has shaped complexity theory for nearly three decades, ruling out “natural” approaches to problems like P vs. NP .

No machine-verified formalization exists in any proof assistant: not in Mathlib, Coq, Isabelle/AFP, or Agda (Section 7).

Our formalization targets Lean 4 with the Mathlib library. The barrier theorem compiles to a six-line tactic proof. The difficulty is in designing the definitions the proof operates on. We make three contributions:

- (1) The first machine-verified formalization of a complexity-theoretic barrier result.
- (2) A systematic account of definition choices: we document three definition choices that enable the mechanized proof and show why natural alternatives fail (Section 4).
- (3) A formalization of the Shannon counting argument, reusing the same circuit abstraction (Section 6).

Section 5 describes what is preserved from the original proof and what is reformulated for mechanizability.

2. INFORMAL BACKGROUND

We briefly recall the statement and proof of the natural proofs barrier, following Razborov and Rudich [6].

Definition 2.1. A *Boolean function* on n variables is a map $f: \{0, 1\}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$. A *Boolean circuit* over the basis $\{\text{AND}, \text{OR}, \text{NOT}\}$ computes such a function; its *size* is the number of gates.

Definition 2.2. A *combinatorial property* \mathcal{P} of n -variable Boolean functions is called *natural* if it satisfies:

- **Constructivity.** Whether f satisfies \mathcal{P} can be decided in time polynomial in 2^n (the truth table length).
- **Largeness.** At least a $1/poly(n)$ fraction of all n -variable Boolean functions satisfy \mathcal{P} .

The property is *useful against $P/poly$* if, for every polynomial p , functions computable by circuits of size $\leq p(n)$ eventually fail to satisfy \mathcal{P} .

Theorem 2.3 (Razborov–Rudich 1997). *If pseudorandom function generators exist, then no natural combinatorial property is useful against P/poly.*

Proof sketch. Suppose \mathcal{P} is natural and useful against P/poly. Let G be a PRF generator with polynomial circuit size bound $c \cdot n^d + c$. Usefulness at this bound provides a cutoff N : for all $n \geq N$, no function with circuits of size $\leq c \cdot n^d + c$ satisfies \mathcal{P} . But constructivity and largeness together imply that \mathcal{P} would be an efficient distinguisher with non-negligible advantage over the PRF, contradicting security. Concretely, at some $n \geq N$, some PRF output $G(n, \text{seed})$ satisfies \mathcal{P} , yet it has a circuit of size $\leq c \cdot n^d + c$. Contradiction. \square

3. FORMALIZATION

Table 1 summarizes the formalization structure. All definitions and proofs compile under Lean 4 v4.29.0-rc6 with Mathlib.

TABLE 1. Formalization structure.

File	Contents	Key definitions
Basic.lean	Boolean functions	BoolFn, truthTable, card_boolFn
Circuit.lean	Circuits	Circuit, eval, size, computes, exists_circuit
ComplexityClass.lean	P/poly	CircuitFamily, PolyBounded, PolyInExp
NaturalProof.lean	Natural properties	CombProperty, constructive, large, useful
PRF.lean	PRF hypothesis	PRFGenerator, PRFHypothesis
NaturalProofBarrier.lean	Main theorem	natural_proof_barrier
Shannon.lean	Counting bound	finite_bounded_circuit, exists_hard_function

3.1. Boolean functions and circuits. A Boolean function on n variables is a Lean function $(\text{Fin } n \rightarrow \text{Bool}) \rightarrow \text{Bool}$. This representation matches circuit evaluation directly: no encoding or decoding is needed at the interface between functions and circuits.

```
abbrev BoolFn (n : ℕ) := (Fin n → Bool) → Bool
```

Circuits are an inductive type over the standard basis:

```
inductive Circuit (n : ℕ) where
| var   : Fin n → Circuit n
| const : Bool → Circuit n
| and   : Circuit n → Circuit n → Circuit n
| or    : Circuit n → Circuit n → Circuit n
| not   : Circuit n → Circuit n
```

Evaluation (`Circuit.eval`) proceeds by structural recursion. Gate count (`Circuit.size`) counts AND, OR, and NOT nodes; inputs and constants contribute zero. A circuit c *computes* f when $\forall x, c.\text{eval } x = f x$.

3.2. Complexity classes. A circuit family assigns one circuit per input length. The size function is *polynomially bounded* if $\exists cd, \forall n, s(n) \leq c \cdot n^d + c$. A function sequence is in P/poly when computed by a polynomially bounded circuit family.

For constructivity, we need a separate notion: the checker circuit size is polynomial in the *truth table length* 2^n , not in the number of variables n . We formalize this as `PolyInExp`:

```
def PolyInExp (s : ℕ → ℕ) : Prop :=
  ∃ c d : ℕ, ∀ n, s n ≤ c * (2 ^ n) ^ d + c
```

The difference between `PolyBounded` and `PolyInExp` is exponential and must be enforced at the type level (Section 4.3).

3.3. Natural properties. A combinatorial property bundles a predicate with decidability:

```
structure CombProperty where
  prop : (n : ℕ) → BoolFn n → Prop
  decidable : (n : ℕ) → DecidablePred (prop n)
```

Constructivity requires a checker circuit family of `PolyInExp` size that agrees with the property on truth table inputs. Largeness requires that the fraction of satisfying functions is $\geq 1/q(n)$ for some polynomially bounded q .

Usefulness is formalized *per polynomial bound*, not per function family (see Section 4.1 for why):

```
def CombProperty.usefulAgainstPPoly (P : CombProperty) : Prop :=
  ∀ c d : ℕ, ∃ N, ∀ n, n ≥ N →
    ∀ (f : BoolFn n) (circ : Circuit n),
      circ.computes f → circ.size ≤ c * n ^ d + c →
        ¬P.prop n f
```

A `NaturalProperty` extends `CombProperty` with proofs of constructivity and largeness.

3.4. PRF hypothesis. A `PRFGenerator` maps seeds to Boolean functions via polynomial-size circuits, with a *uniform* bound $c \cdot n^d + c$ over all seeds:

```
structure PRFGenerator where
  seedLen : ℕ → ℕ
  generate : (n : ℕ) → (Fin (seedLen n) → Bool) → BoolFn n
  polySize : ∃ c d : ℕ, ∀ n (seed : Fin (seedLen n) → Bool),
    ∃ circ : Circuit n,
      circ.computes (generate n seed) ∧
      circ.size ≤ c * n ^ d + c
```

The PRF hypothesis states the consequence of PRF security used in the barrier proof (see Section 4.2 for justification):

```
def PRFHypothesis : Prop :=
  ∃ G : PRFGenerator,
    ∀ (P : CombProperty),
      P.constructive → P.large →
        ∀ N : ℕ, ∃ n, n ≥ N ∧
          ∃ seed : Fin (G.seedLen n) → Bool,
            P.prop n (G.generate n seed)
```

3.5. The barrier theorem. The main theorem and its complete proof:

```
theorem natural_proof_barrier (h : PRFHypothesis) :
  ∀ P : NaturalProperty,
    ¬P.toCombProperty.usefulAgainstPPoly := by
  intro P hU
  obtain ⟨G, hG⟩ := h
  obtain ⟨c_G, d_G, heff⟩ := G.polySize
  obtain ⟨N, hN⟩ := hU c_G d_G
  obtain ⟨n, hn, seed, hsat⟩ :=
```

```

hG P.toCombProperty P.isConstructive P.isLarge N
obtain ⟨circ, hcomp, hsize⟩ := heff n seed
exact hN n hn (G.generate n seed) circ hcomp hsize hsat

```

The proof proceeds in six steps:

- (1) Extract a PRF generator G from the hypothesis.
- (2) Obtain its uniform circuit size bound (c_G, d_G) .
- (3) Apply usefulness at (c_G, d_G) to get a cutoff N .
- (4) The PRF hypothesis, applied to the constructive and large property, yields $n \geq N$ and a seed such that $G(n, seed)$ satisfies \mathcal{P} .
- (5) The efficiency bound gives a circuit for $G(n, seed)$ of size $\leq c_G \cdot n^{d_G} + c_G$.
- (6) Usefulness at $n \geq N$ says no function with such a small circuit satisfies \mathcal{P} , contradicting step 4.

4. DESIGN SPACE: REJECTED ALTERNATIVES

Each definition in Section 3 avoids a mechanization obstacle that blocks simpler formulations.

4.1. Family-level usefulness. A simpler formulation of usefulness quantifies over function families in P/poly :

$$\forall f \in \mathsf{P}/\text{poly}, \exists N, \forall n \geq N, \neg \mathcal{P}(f_n).$$

This formulation fails mechanically: the PRF generator produces outputs indexed by $seed$, so step 4 of the proof yields a specific seed s_0 at a specific n_0 . But usefulness provides a cutoff N that depends on the *family* f . Different seeds yield different families, each with its own cutoff N_s . To reach a contradiction, we need a uniform cutoff that works for all seeds simultaneously, but over infinitely many seeds, no finite maximum exists.

Fix. Quantify over polynomial bounds (c, d) directly:

$$\forall c d, \exists N, \forall n \geq N, (\text{size} \leq c \cdot n^d + c \implies \neg \mathcal{P}).$$

The PRF generator's `polySize` field pins a single (c_G, d_G) . This yields one cutoff N for all seeds, because all seeds share the same circuit size polynomial. The contradiction closes uniformly.

4.2. Probabilistic PRF definition. The textbook PRF definition uses ε -indistinguishability:

$$|\Pr[D(G(k)) = 1] - \Pr[D(f) = 1]| \leq \varepsilon(n),$$

where f is drawn uniformly from all n -variable Boolean functions. Formalizing this requires:

- Probability distributions over $\mathsf{BoolFn} \ n$ (uniform measure on a space of size 2^{2^n}).
- Negligible functions (asymptotic rate conditions).
- The distinguisher-to-property reduction: if \mathcal{P} is constructive, large, and rejects all PRF outputs, one can build a distinguisher with non-negligible advantage.

All three require Mathlib infrastructure that does not yet exist. The distinguisher reduction is the only step that uses the PRF definition's *internal structure*. The barrier proof uses only the *consequence*: if \mathcal{P} is constructive and large, it cannot reject all PRF outputs at arbitrarily large n . Fix. State this consequence directly as `PRFHypothesis`. The barrier proof goes through in six tactic steps. The probabilistic infrastructure would add hundreds of lines of measure-theoretic scaffolding that the barrier theorem does not use.

The consequence form is implied by standard PRF security, so no logical content is lost. Any formalization starting from the standard definition must derive this consequence as an intermediate lemma.

4.3. PolyInExp vs. PolyBounded. Constructivity means the checker runs in time polynomial in the *truth table length* 2^n , not in the number of variables n . The informal proof says “polynomial time” without specifying the parameter. Using `PolyBounded` instead of `PolyInExp` for the checker makes the constructivity condition exponentially too weak: the checker would need to run in time $\text{poly}(n)$, which is sublinear in its 2^n -bit input.

In the formalization, this distinction is enforced at the type level: `constructive` uses `PolyInExp` while `usefulAgainstPPoly` uses `PolyBounded`. A type error would result from swapping them.

5. RELATIONSHIP TO RAZBOROV–RUDICH (1997)

This section distinguishes faithful translations from machine-oriented reformulations in the formalization.

Faithful translations. The contradiction structure is identical to the original: usefulness provides a cutoff below which no small-circuit function satisfies \mathcal{P} ; the PRF hypothesis produces a small-circuit function satisfying \mathcal{P} above that cutoff. Boolean functions, circuits, and the AND/OR/NOT basis match the original. Constructivity and largeness retain their combinatorial content.

Reformulations. The PRF hypothesis is stated in consequence form (Section 4.2) and usefulness per polynomial bound (Section 4.1). Both reformulations drop technical apparatus (probability distributions, circuit family indirection) that the barrier proof does not use, while preserving the logical content of each step.

Scope of reformulation. The overall statement is faithful to the Razborov–Rudich barrier theorem. The reformulations concern how the proof *accesses* its hypotheses.

6. SHANNON COUNTING BOUND

We also formalize the Shannon counting argument: most Boolean functions require large circuits. This result reuses the `Circuit`, `size`, `BoolFn`, and `computes` definitions from the barrier formalization without modification.

Theorem 6.1 (`finite_bounded_circuit`). *For all n, s , the set $\{c : \text{Circuit } n \mid c.\text{size} \leq s\}$ is finite.*

By induction on s . In the base case ($s = 0$), circuits of size zero are exactly variables and constants, a finite set. In the inductive step, circuits of size $\leq s + 1$ are either in the inductive hypothesis set or are built from subcircuits of size $\leq s$ via AND, OR, or NOT, each a finite image of a finite product.

Theorem 6.2 (`finite_computable_bounded`). *For all n, s , the set $\{f : \text{BoolFn } n \mid \exists c, c.\text{computes } f \wedge c.\text{size} \leq s\}$ is finite.*

This follows immediately: the set is a subset of the image of bounded circuits under evaluation.

Theorem 6.3 (`exists_hard_function`). *If the number of functions computable by circuits of size $\leq s$ is less than the total number of n -variable Boolean functions ($= 2^{2^n}$), then there exists a function requiring circuits of size $> s$.*

Suppose for contradiction that every function has a circuit of size $\leq s$. Then `Finset.univ` (all 2^{2^n} functions) is a subset of the finite computable set, contradicting the cardinality hypothesis.

7. RELATED WORK

Complexity theory in proof assistants. The closest precedent is the formalization of the Cook–Levin theorem (NP-completeness of SAT) in Coq by Forster and Kunze [4], which used the call-by-value λ -calculus L as a computational model rather than Turing machines. Balbach [2] independently formalized Cook–Levin in Isabelle/HOL using Turing machines. Forster, Kunze, and Lauermaun [5]

formalized synthetic Kolmogorov complexity in Coq. Those results are positive theorems: NP-completeness, existence of incompressible strings. No complexity barrier has been formalized previously.

Barrier results. The relativization barrier [3] and the algebrization barrier [1] also remain unformalized. Relativization would require formalizing oracle computation, which introduces new types and abstraction layers; we discuss this as future work.

Cryptography in proof assistants. SSProve [7] provides a framework for machine-checked cryptographic proofs in Coq, including PRF-based encryption, using the full probabilistic definition. Our consequence-form PRF hypothesis sidesteps this overhead, since the barrier proof uses only the consequence, as discussed in Section 4.2.

8. CONCLUSION

This paper formalizes the natural proofs barrier in Lean 4, with no `sorry` obligations and approximately 400 lines of code. The definitions do more work than the proofs: choosing interfaces that avoid probabilistic infrastructure is the main obstacle in mechanizing this class of results.

The design space documented in Section 4 records which definition patterns support mechanized proofs of barrier results and which fail.

Future directions. The Shannon counting bound (Section 6) shows that the circuit abstraction applies beyond the barrier theorem. Two extensions that build on the current definitions without modifying them are:

- **Circuit size bounds.** Concrete upper and lower bounds on the number of circuits of given size, enabling explicit Shannon-type lower bounds for specific parameters.
- **Karp–Lipton collapse.** If SAT has polynomial-size circuits, then the polynomial hierarchy collapses.

The relativization and algebrization barriers require oracle computation types, and thus new core abstractions rather than additional lemmas.

Artifact. The complete Lean 4 source code is available at <https://github.com/crabsatellite/lean4-natural-proofs-barrier>. This paper is archived at Zenodo (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19132831).

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